

THE ADHESIVE BONDING OF POLYMERIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The present paper discusses the adhesive bonding of fibre-composites based upon polymeric matrices. The mechanisms of adhesion are discussed, and the surface pretreatment of composite materials prior to bonding is reviewed. Design aspects are also considered.

Keywords: adhesion, adhesives, bonding, composites, design, joints, peel-pplies, surface treatments, thermoplastic matrices, thermoset matrices

INTRODUCTION

Composites based upon thermosetting or thermoplastic polymeric matrices, and containing glass, aramid, or carbon fibres, are being increasingly used in many diverse applications. The former polymers are usually based upon epoxy or polyester resins and are, therefore, more polar than fluorocarbon polymers or polyolefins. This leads to epoxy and polyester matrices possessing relatively high values of surface free energy and this makes them more receptive to adhesive bonding. This is because relatively high values of the surface free energy of the composite substrate will lead to good 'wetting' by the adhesive and to good intrinsic adhesion via the 'adsorption' mechanism of adhesion. The 'adsorption' mechanism of intrinsic adhesion simply proposes that, providing intimate molecular contact between the substrate and adhesive (i.e. good 'wetting') is established, then the intrinsic adhesion may arise from interatomic and intermolecular forces acting across the adhesive/composite interface. Examples of such forces are dispersion forces, dipole forces, hydrogen bond forces and primary chemical (e.g. covalent bonding) forces [1]. On the other hand, the composites based upon thermoplastic polymers typically employ matrices such as poly(ether-ether ketone), poly(ether sulphone), polypropylene, etc. These polymers tend to have low values of surface free energy and hence are difficult to bond using standard engineering adhesives. Hence, for these composites more complex surface pretreatments are often needed prior to bonding when using standard engineering adhesives [1-3], or a different approach to joining such composites is needed. Further, having attained good adhesion with either type of matrix, another aspect of particular interest in the adhesive bonding of fibre-composites arises from a consideration of the detailed design of the bonded joints [1,3-5].

THERMOSETTING POLYMERIC MATRICES

As noted above, thermosetting polymeric matrices are usually receptive to adhesive bonding and also they do not, of course, form oxides or corrode in moist environments. This combination of properties results in surface pretreatments being required which simply remove contaminants such as oils, mould lubricants, or general dirt. There are two main techniques used to achieve this: (i) the peel-ply method and (ii) abrasion and solvent cleaning, often conducted after a peel-ply surface has been exposed.

In the peel-ply method, during manufacture of the laminate, one ply of fabric, such as a woven poly(ethylene terephthalate) fabric, is installed at the bonding surface. Just prior to bonding the peel-ply is removed and, in principle, a clean bondable surface is exposed. However, to enable the peel-ply to be removed, mould release agents are usually applied to the peel-ply. Workers [6,7] have commented that it is extremely difficult to ensure that the peel-ply has not left behind sufficient residual contamination, in the form of the release agent, to reduce both the strength of the adhesively bonded composite and greatly increase the coefficient of variation. Obviously, a residual layer of release agent may act as a weak boundary layer, through which premature joint fracture could readily occur.

To overcome the above problems, it is either necessary to use a peel-ply which does not leave contaminants behind, which often means not using release agents and so makes the peel-ply difficult to remove, or to eliminate the residual contamination. This latter route has been the one typically followed in many industries; and an abrasion treatment, followed by a solvent wipe to remove the abrasion products, has been proved to be most effective [7]. Although, the use of a corona process (which is basically an 'air-plasma' of excited oxygen and ozone radicals and ions) and even acid-etch processes have also been reported [8]. Thus, the main function of a typical peel-ply is to protect the surface until just prior to bonding, at which time an abrasion/solvent cleaning pretreatment is then often considered to be necessary to remove any residual contamination transferred to the composite substrate upon stripping the peel-ply away.

Finally, another problem which may arise upon bonding composites based upon thermosetting polymeric matrices is that absorbed moisture in the composite may be evolved during the adhesive bonding cycle and lead to poor adhesion and air-voids in the adhesive layer [9, 10]. The obvious method of overcoming this problem is to dry out the composite prior to bonding. This is the usual route followed, although it can be difficult and costly to achieve when undertaking repair work. Also, when undertaking adhesive-bonding repairs, it may be necessary to remove absorbed hydraulic oils, etc, from the composite before satisfactory adhesion can be achieved.

THERMOPLASTIC POLYMERIC MATRICES

More recently fibre-composites which are based upon carbon, glass or aramid fibres in a thermoplastic matrix have gained in popularity. Such composites may be formed relatively rapidly using thermoplastic processing techniques and have superior impact properties to those based upon thermosetting matrices. However, work [2,3] has clearly showed that bonding thermoplastic composites, using acrylic and epoxy adhesives, based upon abrasion and solvent cleaning pretreatment techniques leads to significantly lower joint strengths, compared with thermosetting-based composites. The main reason for this observation is the

lack of sufficient adhesion of the adhesive to the thermoplastic-based composite. Thus, either (i) a different route to bond these composites is needed, or (ii) a different, and more effective, form of surface pretreatment is needed prior to bonding.

Considering the former of these options, then the use of a thermoplastic adhesive film of the same polymer type as the matrix of the composite, or a thermoplastic polymer that is mutually soluble with the thermoplastic matrix, may be used to give excellent adhesion between the thermoplastic-film adhesive and the composite [2,11,12]. The intrinsic adhesion in such cases will arise via an 'interdiffusion' mechanism of adhesion. Since, under such circumstances, molecules of the polymeric adhesive and polymeric matrix will interdiffuse and, essentially, lead to an 'interphase' region of co-mingled polymer chains. However, the bonding temperature of such thermoplastic film adhesives is typically relatively high.

On the other hand, conventional structural adhesives based upon epoxies, for example, are not mutually soluble with the typical thermoplastic matrix polymers. Hence, the 'interdiffusion' mechanism of intrinsic adhesion is not a possible route to increasing the intrinsic adhesion. Thus, for such bonding applications, the surface free energy of the thermoplastic matrix polymer needs to be increased significantly. This can be achieved by various pretreatment routes, and two of the most convenient are via corona [2] and oxygen-plasma pretreatments [13]. For example, Kinloch, Kodokian and Watts [2] studied the corona pretreatment of a range of fibre-composites based upon thermoplastic fibre-composites bonded with epoxy adhesives, and used a fracture mechanics method to assess any improvement in the adhesion. They found that, for the corona-pretreated thermoplastic-composite joints, the value of the adhesive fracture energy, G_c , increased steadily as the intensity of the corona treatment was increased until a maximum, plateau value of G_c was reached. There was no evidence of any type of weak boundary layer on the composite nor was there any evidence that the degree of surface roughness induced by the corona treatment had a major effect on the intrinsic adhesion at the adhesive/composite interface. However, it was shown that such a treatment led to an increase in the surface concentration of polar groups, such as oxygen-containing groups, and that this leads to an increase in the surface free energy of the composite substrate. As discussed above, this will result in an increase in both the extent of 'wetting' by the epoxy adhesive and the intrinsic adhesion across the adhesive/composite interface. This enhancement in the intrinsic adhesion was reflected in the locus of failure of the joints no longer being at the adhesive/composite interface, and in far higher values of G_c now being recorded. Further, it was shown that the results from the contact angle measurements (which gave values of the surface free energies of the composites), the X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (which identified the chemical composition of the surface regions of the composite) and the fracture mechanics studies were inter-related. This led to the level of surface polarity needed to attain good 'wetting' and intrinsic adhesion, and hence high values of G_c , being defined. Hence, it was found to be possible to determine (i) whether a given fibre-composite needed to be subjected to a surface pretreatment before bonding, (ii) the level of treatment which was necessary, and also (iii) the effects of aging the pretreated fibre composite before bonding.

ASPECTS OF JOINT DESIGN

Many joint designs involve some form of bonded overlap joint and it is well established [1,5] that the transverse, or cleavage, stresses normal to the plane of the joint (and the loading direction) are invariably a major factor in the fracture of overlap joints. Such stresses arise from the eccentricity of the loading path in the bonded overlap joints. Now, in the case of bonding fibre composites, the presence of these transverse stresses coupled with the low interlaminar tensile strength of composite laminates frequently causes premature joint failure by delamination of the substrates at a relatively low failure load. Indeed, it has been suggested [14] that single-overlap joints should not be used as a basic design for load-bearing joints with composites, unless attached to a moment-resistant support or a very long overlap is used to nullify the effects of the eccentricity in the loading path.

There are many design options to overcome the problems inherent in the single-overlap joint, such as manufacturing scarf overlap, stepped overlap, double overlap and double butt-strap overlap joints [1]. All of these designs have significantly lower values of transverse stresses present when they are subjected to loads. However, it has been found that attention should also be given to the design of the shape of the very ends of the overlap joint, where the transverse stresses tend to be a maximum [1,15]. For example, controlling the detailed shape of the adhesive spew fillet may greatly reduce the level of the transverse stresses, and so result in an increase in joint strength [1,3,4].

Finally, much progress has recently been made in standardising the fracture mechanics test methods [16] for assessing the fracture energy, G_c , of adhesively-bonded joints, and using such methods to assess the service life of such bonded composite-structures when subjected to cyclic-fatigue [17] and mode II loads [18].

CONCLUSIONS

The adhesive bonding of fibre composites based upon polymeric matrices requires that attention is given to the choice of preparing the surface prior to bonding. The pretreatments which may be needed for either original manufacture, or for repair, are well established and are not technologically complex. However, their introduction and use in practice may introduce significant extra costs into the manufacture, or repair, process. Careful consideration also needs to be given to the design of adhesive joints involving composite materials. Since the relatively low transverse strengths of composites necessitates that the transverse stresses in the joint are minimised in order to achieve high failure loads.

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